

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VOLZ****FIRST NAME: TOBIAS****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 10

WRITING AN ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing a paper can be challenging if the author does not know the basic rules of academic writing, citation, and formatting. To ensure that all students have the skills to structure papers correctly and to apply relevant rules, EUCLID implemented a mandatory course on academic writing as the first module for all its students. The study material consists of a document with useful information, such as paper writing, how to avoid plagiarism, citation, and formatting. Besides the study material, the students have access to a video tutorial on how to use EUCLID's templates.

This response paper will give a brief overview of EUCLID's relevant rules and regulations for academic journals, focusing on essential tips for papers in the master's program in mediation and conflict resolution. Through this summary of the information provided in the learning material, the reader will furthermore get hands-on advice on how to apply these rules. The response paper will end with a personal conclusion about what I learned while studying EUCLID's ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1.

2) WHAT IS AN EXCELLENT PAPER?

The course material consists of an 83-pages long compilation of different documents, with topics mainly focusing on how to write an excellent paper. To produce a unique paper, the writer needs, according to the EUCLID ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1, to start from using the EUCLID Word template. The use of the model, also utilized in this response paper, can ensure that the writer applies the expected correct styles. It is furthermore essential to use US or UK spelling and punctuation consistently. Apart from

grammar and spelling differences, US spelling has its own rules for punctuation as well. The main difference is that the US punctuation is inside quotes. Furthermore, one should always run a spell check after developing the first draft. (EUCLID 2015, 6-7). To ensure proper spell check, EUCLID provides a free version of the spell check software Grammarly.

Plagiarism, when a writer uses sources of information without crediting the author of that source, should be avoided. On the one hand, plagiarism is not just unethical and unfair, but on the other hand, also a serious academic offense that can be followed by negative consequences for the writer who did not cite sources according to academic standards. Academic citing rules shall be applied to indicate where one found a piece of information to avoid plagiarism. The citation can be done in-text or through a list of works cited. If one uses the same words as an author, a quotation with quotation marks are needed. Quotes, however, shall not be used too much as it then does not look like one's research (EUCLID 2015, 8-20).

As stated in the course material:

Plagiarism comes in two forms, both unacceptable. First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks, not just a footnote. Moreover, you should not present a close paraphrase from a source: either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words (EUCLID 2015, 44).

Other rules, tips, and recommendations include writing clearly by using short sentences, avoiding long paragraphs, and always similar sentence structures. The introduction of a stylistic variety, for example, by not starting every sentence with a subject, can be one way to make a paper more interesting to read. Stay focused on the paper and only assess selected parts of a theory. One needs to accurately describe the relevant aspects of the method one wants to assess. Do not try to provide an overview of the whole theory (EUCLID 2015, 43-51).

The course material gives the following example:

For example, if you are writing in criticism of John Rawls's 'difference principles,' you should not try to sketch his theory of the original position and the argument for the principle within the original position. Confine yourself to the aspects of Rawls's view that are of immediate relevance to his account of fair distribution. Anything else will be a distraction, and, in the short space available, is not likely to be done well (EUCLID 2015, 43).

EUCLID's Coursepack Period 1 furthermore gives the reader recommendations on how to correctly use commas. Of particular interest to me was the details and examples on to use a comma to join two independent clauses and to use commas to bracket nonrestrictive and non-essential parts of phrases. However, do not use commas to bracket sentences, that are essential to paragraph's meaning (EUCLID 2015, 46).

New to me were the tips on the proper uses of "it's" and "its" highlighting that "it's" is a contraction meaning, and "its" shows a possessive form of "it." The same rule

applies to “your” as the possessive form of “you” and “you’re” as the contraction meaning of “you are” (EUCLID 2015, 47).

Additionally, views of authors and political philosophers one writes about need to be taken seriously. One way to do so is to ask oneself as a writer how the author of the text one is reading would react to the criticism one may have. The writer needs to develop a sense of the author’s internal integrity. While criticizing a text, one needs to keep in mind that the sources one has read are the outcome of an often long and well-reflected writing process. This process often included that the writer distributed drafts of the book, article or manuscript to experts, friends, family or other people to receive their feedback and included their comments in the writing. It does not necessarily mean that the author is always right. However, the written product is usually well reflected (EUCLID 2015, 44).

I found the suggestion to read out the paper draft loudly very helpful and to correct sentences that might not sound right or understandable. Other rules and recommendations include writing clearly by using short sentences, avoiding long paragraphs, wrong use of commas, and complicated sentence structures. If a sentence is too long, it is advisable to find a way to split it into several sentences. The course material of EUCLID recommends avoiding obscure words or poetry-style (EUCLID 2015, 43-51).

3) **CONCLUSION**

Even though I have written academic papers as a part of my studies and career in the field of international development, I found the first period of EUCLID’s ACA-401 introduction to academic writing course beneficial and would recommend this course. I was especially impressed by the reader-friendly structure of the material, the variety of given examples, and the detailed explanations of various concepts. Not only did they help refresh my knowledge, but it also gave me new insights into writing a good paper. I feel motivated to apply new skills to improve my academic writing. Last but not least, I look forward to receiving constructive feedback on the documents I will produce.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1*.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/> (accessed on 28.01.2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.